

ANTECEDENTS AND CONSEQUENCES OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ON CUSTOMER PURCHASE INTENTION

A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract: The purpose of this paper is to investigate the impact of social media marketing on customer purchase intention with a focus on its antecedents and consequences. By analyzing the research trends, dimensions and outcomes, the social media marketing-customer purchase intention relationship is synthesized and future research direction is recommended. A conceptual roadmap that portrays the relationship is suggested. The review is based on 50 articles published during 2010 – 2024. It follows a systematic approach and presents the publication trends based on region, sector, time, database, journals, along with antecedents and consequences through content analysis. The analysis draws on various dimensions of social media marketing and customer purchase intention. The study identified nine contemporary antecedents of social media marketing that include customization, entertainment, e-WOM, informativeness, interaction, trendiness, trust, perceived value and social media influencers; and two widely used outcomes which include purchase intention and customer purchase intention. Future research suggestions include carrying out research in regions other than Asia and Europe. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is one of the few attempts to offer most comprehensive and collective scholarship to this subject area.

Keywords: Systematic literature review; social media marketing; customer purchase intention; purchase intention

1.0 Introduction

The widespread use of social media in people's daily lives today and its power to influence decisions has a big influence on consumers' intentions to make purchases (Chrisniyanti & Fah, 2022; Nguyen et al., 2020). People utilise social media, according to Jamil et al. (2021) and Anas et al. (2023), to research items, compare prices, get suggestions from friends, keep up with current trends, and even make direct purchases via social media sites like Facebook and Instagram. Businesses must now reevaluate their marketing strategies and adapt to the ever-changing wants of their audience as a result of this shift in the purchasing process. Customer buying intentions, particularly customer purchase intention (CPI), are heavily impacted by trendiness, entertainment, interactivity, customisation, and electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) in social media marketing (SMM) (Shofiya & Fachira, 2021; Ebrahimi et al., 2022). Businesses can increasingly use social media to provide more personalised experiences for customers, target particular groups with marketing, and interact directly with customers through comments and reviews (Cheung et al., 2021). Engaging visual resources such as GIFs, movies, and photographs can maintain customers' interest in a business and its products or services (Yoong & Lian, 2019; Hanaysha, 2022). According to Anas et al. (2023), businesses can foster enduring relationships with their clientele by offering valuable information and engaging with them on social media platforms. Ultimately, the impact of social media has altered how consumers choose which products and services to buy. Social media marketing components can also have a significant impact on a company's long-term viability (Sadom et al., 2023). Employing social media platforms to interact with their target audience and advertise their products and services can help businesses become more visible, connect with more potential clients, reduce marketing expenses, and increase sales revenue. This enhances their ability to withstand financial setbacks and maintains their competitiveness in the market (Anas et al., 2023; Nguyen et al., 2024). Social media can also be used to promote corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives. Social sustainability can be enhanced by CSR initiatives by addressing societal issues and fostering stronger stakeholder relationships (Anas et al., 2023).

This study is therefore going to benefit business practitioners, researchers, professionals and policy makers. Hence need for continued research in the area of social media marketing on purchase intention to gain insights to inform future business practitioners, researchers, professionals and policy makers. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to compile the scholarly work on social media marketing on customer purchase intention under one body advancing three research questions:

RQ1: What are the research trends in social media marketing on customer purchase intention by country, sector, time, database and journals?

RQ2: What are the antecedents and consequences of social media marketing on customer purchase intention?

RQ3: What are the implications and research gaps identified in the existing literature on the impact of social media marketing on customer purchase intention?

2.0 Research methodology

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria follow the adapted Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) model having less than the 27 recommended items in the original PRISMA model. All journal articles have been published during the time period of 2010 - 2024. All the articles are full-text articles, accessible by anyone using a Harzing's "Publish or Perish" Crossref. Each article is in line with the title and objectives of the study.

Search Strings based on 1 string:

"Impact of social media marketing factors on customer purchase intention"

Identification of References:

Search strings have been designed by taking into consideration keywords adopted for research for the initial identification of references. The search strings used and total references identified initially have been highlighted in the table below:

Table 2.1: The search strings used and total references

Search String	Harzing's "Publish or Perish" Crossref
"Impact of social media marketing factors on customer purchase intention"	1,000
Total Articles before elimination	1,000

Thus, a total of 1,000 references have been selected from the search strings in Harzing's "Publish or Perish" Crossref. The exclusion stage involved eliminating: all articles not cited at all within a year (N=487), articles cited once within a year (N=123), articles not in English language (N=5), duplicates (N=13), articles not related to social media marketing and customer purchase intention (N=291), articles not multi-item scale assessing social media marketing and customer purchase intention (N=30), and others like meta-analysis (N=1), leaving 50 valid articles for final analysis. The inclusion criteria covers: articles that assesses one or more social media marketing-customer purchase intention relationships using multi-item scales, included a measure of customer purchase intention or purchase intention, conducted in the context of social media marketing and cited at least 2 times or more within a year. The whole process of exclusion-inclusion criteria is as indicated in Figure 1 below:

Figure 2.1: Systematic literature review flowchart

3.0 Results

What are the research trends in social media marketing on customer purchase intention by country, sector, time, database and journals?

In this section, the identified 50 articles are elaborated on the basis of country, sector or industry, time of publication, database and journals.

3.1 Distribution of articles on the basis of country

On the basis of country, 50 research articles including empirical and conceptual were published in different countries as per their distribution described in Figure 2. Majority of the articles were published in Indonesia (n=9), followed by Malaysia (n=5), India, Pakistan, China and Jordan each having 4 publications. Bahrain, Bangladesh, Saudi Arabia, South Korea, UAE and others each has 2 publications. The remaining countries like Afghanistan, Brazil, Egypt, Hong Kong, Ireland, Italy, Kosovo, Latvia, Nepal, North Cyprus, Romania, South Africa, Thailand and Turkey each has 1 publication. Three publications were made in more than one country, for instance Noreen & Han (2015) covered South Korea and Pakistan; Al-Alawi et al. (2020) included Saudi Arabia and Bahrain; and Wagdi et al. (2022) involved Brazil, Egypt, India, South Africa and Turkey.

Figure 3.1: Distribution of Articles on the basis of country
Source: Author’s Research

3.2 Distribution of articles on the basis of sector/Industry

Out of the 50 articles in Figure 3, “General purpose sector” (others) has the highest number of publications (n=19), followed by “Luxury Brands Industry” (n=6), “Cosmetics Industry” (n=3) and “Fast Food Industry” (n=3). “Automobile Industry”, “Education Services”, “ICT Industry” and “Tourism Sectors” each shares 2 papers. The remaining sectors of “Airlines Industry”, “Apparel Industry”, “Banking Industry”, “Beauty Centres”, “Digital Markets”, “Events Industry”, “Fashion Industry”, “Green Industry”, “Services Industry”, “Smartphones Market” and “Telecom Industry” each shares 1 paper.

Figure 3.2: Distribution of articles on the basis of sector
Source: Author’s Research

3.3 Distribution of articles on the basis of publication time from 2010-2024

As seen from Figure 4, in the early years from 2010 to 2015, there were few publications in the area of social media marketing. However, the trend changed positively from 2017 onwards much as there was a slight decline in 2021 and 2023

Figure 3.3: Distribution of articles on the basis of Publication time
Source: Author's Research

3.4 Distribution of articles on the basis of database

Figure 5 shows a clear distribution of all the 50 articles on the basis of database. The leading publication databases with highest number of articles include "Growing Science" (n=6) and "Informa UK Limited" (n=6). These are closely followed by "IEEE" (n=4), "Elsevier" (n=4) and "Emerald" (n=4). "Inderscience Publishers" has 3 articles, "MDPI AG" 2 articles, "IGI Global" 2 articles, "Nepal Journals Online" 2 articles, and all the remaining databases each has 1 article.

Figure 3.4: Distribution of articles on the basis of database
Source: Author's Research

3.5 Frequency of occurrence of articles by journal types

The distribution of published articles based on journal types is shown in Figure 6. From the journal wise distribution of articles, it is discovered that “International Journal of Data and Network Science” has the highest number of papers (n=5), followed by “Journal of Global Fashion Marketing” with (n=3) papers, “Arab Gulf Journal of Scientific Research” (n=2), “Asia Marketing Journal” (n=2), Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics” (n=2), “International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising” (n=2), and “Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences” (n=2). The remaining journals like “Sustainability”, “Journal of Promotion Management”, “Journal of Economics, Management and Trade”, etc each share (n=1) paper. It should be noted that 4 papers were conference proceedings.

Figure 3.5: Distribution of articles on the basis of Journals
Source: Author's Research

3.6 The conceptual framework

What are the antecedents and consequences of social media marketing on customer purchase intention?

3.7 Dimensions of social media marketing

Many researchers have determined the dimensions of social media marketing. For example, communication, information exchange, and collaboration are the three characteristics of social media marketing that are documented by Jahid et al. (2021). Five aspects of social media marketing—entertainment, interaction, trendiness, personalisation, and perceived risk—were covered by Seo and Park (2018). On the other hand, Kim and Ko (2010) distinguished five aspects of social media marketing: e-WOM, trendiness, customisation, entertainment, and interaction. Similar to this, social media marketing comprises social media influencers, perceived value, e-word-of-mouth, trendiness, customisation, entertainment, and interaction (Gan & Wang, 2017; Bilgin, 2018; Wang et al., 2019; Ebrahim, 2020; Ao et al., 2023). Trendiness, perceived value, personalisation, and interaction were all used by Sano (2015) as components of social media marketing for the insurance sector. In contrast, Hermanda et al. (2019) used four characteristics of social media influencers—visibility, credibility, attraction, and power—to examine how social media influencers affected cosmetic customers' brand image, self-concept, and intention to purchase. The fast food and beverage industry's social media marketing characteristics were categorised into five groups by Aji et al. (2020) and Shofiya & Fachira (2021): entertainment, interaction, trendiness, advertisement, and customisation. While some scholars (Emini & Zeqiri, 2021; Savitri et al., 2022; Dewi et al., 2022) view social media marketing as a unidimensional concept, the majority of researchers (Kim & Ko, 2010; Balakrishnan et al., 2014; Gautam & Sharma, 2017; Alalwan, 2018; Onofrei et al., 2022) regard it as a multidimensional concept.

In this study, the various dimensions of social media marketing identified by various scholars as per Figure 7 and Table 1 include brand communication, brand consciousness, direct communication, corporate reputation, customer reviews, customization, entertainment, electronic word of mouth (E-WOM), expertise, firm created content, information quality, information sharing, informativeness, interaction, perceived content quality, perceived financial value, perceived functional value, perceived relevance, perceived risk, personalization, product information beliefs, social media advertisement, social media marketing, social media motivation, trendiness, trust etc.

The most prominent antecedents of social media marketing given by authors coverage include E-WOM (n=21, Interaction (n=17), Entertainment (n=13), Trendiness (n=12), Customization (n=9), Trust (n=7), Social Media Marketing (n=6), and Informativeness (n=5). Those considered 3 times by the researchers include: perceived usefulness, personalization, social media advertisement, online communities and user generated content. Those considered 2 times by the scholars are blogs, brand consciousness, ease of communication through social media, information sharing, materialism beliefs, perceived relevance, perceived risk, product information beliefs, social commerce construct, and value corruption beliefs. The rest of the dimensions are considered once as illustrated in (Table 1).

Some of the identified antecedents of social media marketing with their authors include E-WOM (Noreen & Han ,2015; Wong, 2018; Kim & Ko, 2010; Gautam & Sharma, 2017; Moslehpour et al. ,2020; Khan et al.,2021; Wagdi et al., 2022); Interaction (Kim & Ko, 2010; Gautam & Sharma, 2017; Moslehpour et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2022; Imtiaz et al., 2019; Wagdi et al., 2022; Salhab et al., 2023; Alsoud et al., 2023); Entertainment (Kim & Ko ,2010; Gautam & Sharma ,2017; Moslehpour et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2022; Aggarwal & Mittal, 2022; Hanaysha, 2022); Trendiness (Kim & Ko, 2010; Gautam & Sharma, 2017; Moslehpour et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2022; Aggarwal & Mittal, 2022; Alsoud et al., 2023; Customization (Kim & Ko, 2010; Moslehpour et al., 2020; Gautam & Sharma, 2017; Sharma et al., 2022; Alsoud et al., 2023; Ghafourzay & Parilt, 2020); Trust (Sin et al., 2012; Manzoor et al.,2020; Wong, 2018; Shrestha, 2020; Sodom et al., 2023); Social Media Marketing (Savitri et al., 2022; Emini & Zeqiri, 2021; Dewi et al., 2022; Putra & Aprilson, 2022; and Informativeness (Aggarwal & Mittal, 2022; Hanaysha, 2022; Zhang et al., 2019; Supotthamjaree & Srinaruewan, 2021; Alalwan, 2018).

Figure 3.6: Dimensions of social media marketing
Source: Author’s Research

Table 3.1: Antecedents of social media marketing

Antecedents	References
Ability to communicate through social media	Sijabat et al. (2020)
Advertising	Mazeed & Kodumagulla (2019)
Altruistic motivations	Pop et al. (2020)
Attitude toward social media advertising	Pandey et al. (2018)
Attitudes	Pop et al. (2020)
Attractiveness	Hmoud et al. (2022)
Blogs	Wagdi et al. (2022), Salhab et al. (2023)
Brand communication	Almohaimmeed (2019)
Brand consciousness	Chu et al. (2013), Chu et al. (2019)
Brand perception	Pütter (2017)
Communication	Imtiaz et al. (2019)
Consumer trust	Kumar & Sharma (2020)
Corporate reputation	Almohaimmeed (2019)
Credibility	Supotthamjaree & Srinaruewan (2021)
Customer awareness	Shrestha (2020)
Customer engagement	Shrestha (2020)
Customer online engagement	Kumaradeepan et al. (2023)
Customer reviews	Wagdi et al. (2022)
Customer social support	Manzoor et al. (2020)
Customization	Kim & Ko (2010), Moslehpour et al. (2020), Gautam & Sharma (2017), Sharma et al. (2022), Alsoud et al. (2023), Ghafourzay & Pariltı (2020), Bukhori et al. (2022), Ibrahim (2023), Sadom et al. (2023)
Direct communication	Wagdi et al. (2022)
Ease of communication through social media	Sijabat et al. (2020)
Egoistic motivations	Pop et al. (2020)
Email marketing	Bismo et al. (2019)
Engagement	Chuah et al. (2023)
Entertainment	Kim & Ko (2010), Gautam & Sharma (2017), Moslehpour et al. (2020), Sharma et al. (2022), Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Hanaysha (2022), Ghafourzay & Pariltı (2020), Bukhori et al. (2022), Supotthamjaree & Srinaruewan (2021), Ibrahim (2023), Chuah et al. (2023), Sadom et al. (2023), Kumaradeepan et al. (2023)
EWOM	Noreen & Han (2015), Wong (2018), Kim & Ko (2010), Balakrishnan et al. (2014), Gautam & Sharma (2017), Moslehpour et al. (2020), Khan et al. (2021), Pandey et al. (2018), Imtiaz et al. (2019), Wagdi et al. (2022), Salhab et al. (2023), Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Zhang et al. (2019), Alsoud et al. (2023), Ghafourzay & Pariltı (2020), Mazeed & Kodumagulla (2019), Ibrahim (2023), Chuah et al. (2023), Sadom et al. (2023), Kumaradeepan et al. (2023), Sharma et al. (2022)
Experience provided by social media	Sijabat et al. (2020)
Expertise	Hmoud et al. (2022)
Falsify/no sense beliefs	Chu et al. (2019)
Firm Created Content	Morra et al. (2017)
Frequency of social media updates	Almohaimmeed (2019)
Fun in using social media	Sijabat et al. (2020)
Hoarding	Mazeed & Kodumagulla (2019)
Information access effects	Supotthamjaree & Srinaruewan (2021)
Information provided on products	Sijabat et al. (2020)
Information Quality	Hmoud et al. (2022)
Information sharing	Imtiaz et al. (2019),
Informativeness	Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Hanaysha (2022), Zhang et al. (2019), Supotthamjaree & Srinaruewan (2021) Alalwan (2018)
Interaction	Kim & Ko (2010), Gautam & Sharma (2017), Moslehpour et al. (2020), Sharma et al. (2022), Imtiaz et al. (2019), Wagdi et al. (2022), Salhab et al. (2023), Alsoud et al. (2023), Ghafourzay & Pariltı (2020), Bukhori et al. (2022), Ibrahim (2023), Sadom et al. (2023), Kumaradeepan et al. (2023), Onofrei et al. (2022), Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Hanaysha (2022), Alalwan (2018)

Interesting social media content	Sijabat et al. (2020)
Level of satisfaction with provided information	Sijabat et al. (2020)
Materialism beliefs	Chu et al. (2013), Chu et al. (2019)
Meaning Transfer	Hmoud et al. (2022)
Online advertisement	Balakrishnan et al. (2014)
Online communities	Balakrishnan et al. (2014), Wagdi et al. (2022), Salhab et al. (2023)
Peer communication	Pandey et al. (2018)
Perceived content quality	Onofrei et al. (2022)
Perceived financial value	Yu & Zheng (2021)
Perceived functional value	Yu & Zheng (2021)
Perceived green value	Sun & Xing (2022)
Perceived individual value	Yu & Zheng (2021)
Perceived relevance	Alalwan (2018), Hanaysha (2022)
Perceived risk	Wong (2018), AlAlawi et al. (2020)
Perceived social value	Yu & Zheng (2021)
Perceived source credibility	Onofrei et al. (2022)
Perceived source homophily	Onofrei et al. (2022)
Perceived usefulness	Sin et al. (2012), Kumar & Sharma (2020), Wong (2018)
Personalization	Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Zhang et al. (2019), Chuah et al. (2023)
Product information beliefs	Chu et al. (2013), Chu et al. (2019)
Product/services perception	Shrestha (2020)
Reputation	Sadom et al. (2023)
Sharing data	Manzoor et al. (2020)
Social commerce construct	Sin et al. (2012), Kumar & Sharma (2020)
Social influence	AlAlawi et al. (2020)
Social media	Bismo et al. (2019)
Social media advertisement	Noreen & Han (2015), Pütter (2017), Galdeano et al. (2019)
Social media Apps design and content quality	AlAlawi et al. (2020)
Social media-based brand equity	Galdeano et al. (2019)
Social media-based brand image	Galdeano et al. (2019)
Social media information sharing	Sun & Xing (2022)
Social media marketing	Savitri et al. (2022), Emini & Zeqiri (2021), Dewi et al. (2022), Putra & Aprilson (2022), Ellitan et al. (2022), Wagdi et al. (2022)
Social media marketing content type	Almohaimmeed (2019)
Social media motivation	Almohaimmeed (2019)
Social media usage	Khan et al. (2021)
Social media use for information	Hu & Zhu (2022)
Social media use for socializing	Hu & Zhu (2022)
Social network marketing	Prabowo et al. (2020)
Subjective norms	Pop et al. (2020)
Tailored advertising	Salhab et al. (2023)
Trendiness	Kim & Ko (2010), Gautam & Sharma (2017), Moslehpour et al. (2020), Sharma et al. (2022), Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Alsoud et al. (2023), Ghafourzay & Pariltı (2020), Bukhori et al. (2022), Ibrahim (2023), Chuah et al. (2023), Sadom et al. (2023), Kumaradeepan et al. (2023)
Trust	Sin et al. (2012), Manzoor et al. (2020), Wong (2018), Shrestha (2020), Sadom et al. (2023), Kumaradeepan et al. (2023), Hmoud et al. (2022)
User generated content	Wagdi et al. (2022), Salhab et al. (2023), Morra et al. (2017)
Value corruption beliefs	Chu et al. (2013), Chu et al. (2019)
Viral marketing	Salhab et al. (2023)
Websites quality	Manzoor et al. (2020)

3.8 Consequences of customer purchase intention

The phrase "customer purchase intention" refers to a client's propensity to make a purchase as well as their concerns (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Purchase intention, according to Blackwell et al. (2006), is the anticipation of what will be bought. A person's attitude and preference towards a product or service are highly correlated with their intention to purchase it (Kim and Ko, 2012; Chrisniyanti & Fah, 2022). Wu et al. (2011) defined purchase intention as the probability that consumers will intend to purchase a particular good or service in the future. Purchase intention is the probability that a user would make a purchase based on follower recommendations after using social media platforms (Choedon & Lee, 2020; Anas et al., 2023).

As shown in Table 2, this review identifies multiple consequences or outcomes of customer purchase intention that include consumer buying intention (Pütter, 2017); consumer purchase intention (Manzoor et al., 2020; Imtiaz et al., 2019; Sijabat et al., 2020); customer purchase intention (Hmoud et al., 2022; Ghafourzay & Parilti, 2020; Bukhori et al., 2022); green consumption intention (Wagdi et al. (2022); green purchase intention (Sun & Xing, 2022; Pop et al., 2020); online purchase intention (Al-Alawi et al. (2020); purchase decision (Hanaysha, 2022); purchase intention (Kim & Ko, 2010; Alalwan, 2018; Balakrishnan et al., 2014; Onofrei et al., 2022; Sin et al., 2012); Purchase intention of fast food products (Sadom et al., 2023); Purchase intention of luxury brands (Chu et al., 2019); Tourists' Purchase Intention (Alsoud et al., 2023); and brand loyalty (Kumaradeepan et al., 2023). As indicated in Table 2, the analysis reveals that the most identified variable or outcome is purchase intention (Kim & Ko, 2010; Alalwan, 2018; Balakrishnan et al., 2014; Onofrei et al., 2022; Sin et al., 2012); followed by customer purchase intention (Hmoud et al., 2022; Ghafourzay & Parilti, 2020; Bukhori et al., 2022).

Table 3.2: Consequences of Customer Purchase Intention

Consequences	References
Brand loyalty	Kumaradeepan et al. (2023)
Consumer buying intention	Pütter (2017)
Consumer purchase intention	Manzoor et al. (2020), Imtiaz et al. (2019), Sijabat et al. (2020), Wong (2018), Prabowo et al. (2020), Gautam & Sharma (2017), Sharma et al. (2022)
Customer purchase intention	Hmoud et al. (2022), Ghafourzay & Parilti (2020), Bukhori et al. (2022)
Green consumption intention	Wagdi et al. (2022)
Green purchase intention	Sun & Xing (2022), Pop et al. (2020)
Online purchase intention	AlAlawi et al. (2020)
Purchase decision	Hanaysha (2022)
Purchase intention	Kim & Ko (2010), Alalwan (2018), Balakrishnan et al. (2014), Onofrei et al. (2022), Sin et al. (2012), Moslehpour et al. (2020), Yu & Zheng (2021), Morra et al. (2017), Khan et al. (2021), Savitri et al. (2022), Pandey et al. (2018), Hu & Zhu (2022), Emini & Zeqiri (2021), Bismo et al. (2019), Almohaimmeed (2019), Salhab et al. (2023), Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Kumar & Sharma (2020) Zhang et al. (2019), Dewi et al. (2022), Noreen & Han (2015), Shrestha (2020), Supotthamjaree & Srinaruewan (2021), Mazed & Kodumagulla (2019), Ibrahim (2023), Chuah et al. (2023), Putra & Aprilson (2022), Ellitan et al. (2022), Galdeano et al. (2019)
Purchase intention of fast-food products	Sadom et al. (2023)
Purchase intention of luxury brands	Chu et al. (2019)
Tourists' Purchase Intention	Alsoud et al. (2023)

3.9 Antecedents of social media marketing and their relationship with customer purchase intention

Numerous studies (Shofiya & Fachira, 2021; Emini & Zeqiri, 2021; Ebrahimi et al., 2021; Ebrahimi et al., 2022; Bushara et al., 2023; Anas et al., 2023) have examined the relationship between social media marketing and customer purchase intention and have found a significant influence. Several social media marketing aspects have a substantial impact on customers' intentions to purchase (Ebrahimi et al., 2022; Bushara et al., 2023; Anas et al., 2023). First, these activities can be used to promote sustainable practices and products by raising customer awareness and interest in these participants. Cheung et al. (2019), Sun & Xing (2022), and Chrisniyanti & Fah (2022) suggest that this could therefore influence their buying decisions and raise demand for their products and services. Social media marketing may also be used to communicate a company's proposition to its stakeholders, which helps build consumer credibility and confidence. This could lead to a rise in brand loyalty and positive perceptions of the company's products, which could influence consumers' propensity to make a purchase (Dessert et al., 2015; Shofiya & Fachira, 2021; Ebrahimi et al., 2022; Anas et al., 2023). Social media marketing gives businesses access to customer input and ideas for how to enhance their product offers, which raises the possibility that a customer will make a purchase (Merrilees, 2016; Husnain et al., 2017; Shofiya & Fachira, 2021; Anas et al., 2023).

This review confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between antecedents of social media marketing and customer purchase intention (Table 3). This is supported by most of the variables posting positive relationships. For instance, under customization (Kim & Ko, 2010; Moslehpour et al., 2020; Gautama & Sharma, 2017; Sharma et al., 2022); entertainment (Kim & Ko, 2010; Gautam & Sharma, 2017; Moslehpour et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2022; Aggarwal & Mittal, 2022); E-WOM (Noreen & Han, 2015; Wong, 2018; Kim & Ko, 2010; Balakrishnan et al., 2014; Gautam & Sharma, 2017; Moslehpour et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021; Pandey et al., 2018; Imtiaz et al., 2019; Wagdi et al., 2022); informativeness (Aggarwal & Mittal, 2022; Hanaysha, 2022; Zhang et al., 2019); interaction (Kim & Ko, 2010; Gautam & Sharma, 2017; Moslehpour et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2022; Imtiaz et al., 2019; Wagdi et al., 2022; Salhab et al., 2023); trendiness (Kim & Ko, 2010; Gautam & Sharma, 2017; Moslehpour et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2022; Aggarwal & Mittal, 2022); and trust (Sin et al., 2012; Manzoor et al., 2020; Shrestha, 2020; Sadom et al., 2023) all posited significant positive relationships. However, Hanaysha (2022) got negative results when using entertainment.

Additionally, Alsoud et al. (2023) results were not supported when applying E-WOM on customer purchase intention. Wong (2018) when relating trust variable to customer purchase intention got negative results.

Table 3.3: Antecedents of social media marketing and their relationship with customer purchase intention

Antecedents	References	Findings
Ability to communicate through social media	Sijabat et al. (2020)	Positive
Advertising	Mazeed & Kodumagulla (2019)	Positive
Altruistic motivations	Pop et al. (2020)	Positive
Attitude toward social media advertising	Pandey et al. (2018)	Positive
Attitudes	Pop et al. (2020)	Positive
Attractiveness	Hmoud et al. (2022)	Positive
Blogs	Wagdi et al. (2022), Salhab et al. (2023)	Positive
Brand communication	Almohaimmeed (2019)	Positive
Brand consciousness	Chu et al. (2013), Chu et al. (2019)	Positive
Brand perception	Pütter (2017)	Positive
Communication	Imtiaz et al. (2019)	Positive
Consumer trust	Kumar & Sharma (2020)	Positive
Corporate reputation	Almohaimmeed (2019)	Positive
Credibility	Supotthamjaree & Srinaruewan (2021)	Positive
Customer awareness	Shrestha (2020)	Positive
Customer engagement	Shrestha (2020)	Positive
Customer online engagement	Kumaradeepan et al. (2023)	Positive
Customer reviews	Wagdi et al. (2022)	Positive
Customer social support	Manzoor et al. (2020)	Positive
Customization	Kim & Ko (2010), Moslehpour et al. (2020), Gautam & Sharma (2017), Sharma et al. (2022), Alsoud et al. (2023), Ghafourzay & Pariltı (2020), Bukhori et al. (2022), Ibrahim (2023), Sadom et al. (2023)	Positive
Direct communication	Wagdi et al. (2022)	Positive
Ease of communication through social media	Sijabat et al. (2020)	Positive
Egoistic motivations	Pop et al. (2020)	Positive
Email marketing	Bismo et al. (2019)	Positive
Engagement	Chuah et al. (2023)	Positive
Entertainment	Kim & Ko (2010), Gautam & Sharma (2017), Moslehpour et al. (2020), Sharma et al. (2022), Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Ghafourzay & Pariltı (2020), Bukhori et al. (2022), Supotthamjaree & Srinaruewan (2021), Ibrahim (2023), Chuah et al. (2023), Sadom et al. (2023), Kumaradeepan et al. (2023)	Positive
Entertainment	Hanaysha (2022)	Negative
EWOM	Noreen & Han (2015), Wong (2018), Kim & Ko (2010), Balakrishnan et al. (2014), Gautam & Sharma (2017), Moslehpour et al. (2020), Khan et al. (2021), Pandey et al. (2018), Imtiaz et al. (2019), Wagdi et al. (2022), Salhab et al. (2023), Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Zhang et al. (2019), Ghafourzay & Pariltı (2020), Mazeed & Kodumagulla (2019), Ibrahim (2023), Chuah et al. (2023), Sadom et al. (2023), Kumaradeepan et al. (2023), Sharma et al. (2022)	Positive
EWOM	Alsoud et al. (2023)	Negative
Experience provided by social media	Sijabat et al. (2020)	Positive
Expertise	Hmoud et al. (2022)	Positive
Falsify/no sense beliefs	Chu et al. (2019)	Positive
Firm Created Content	Morra et al. (2017)	Positive
Frequency of social media updates	Almohaimmeed (2019)	Positive
Fun in using social media	Sijabat et al. (2020)	Positive
Hoarding	Mazeed & Kodumagulla (2019)	Positive
Information access effects	Supotthamjaree & Srinaruewan (2021)	Positive
Information provided on products	Sijabat et al. (2020)	Positive
Information Quality	Hmoud et al. (2022)	Positive
Information sharing	Imtiaz et al. (2019), Wagdi et al. (2022)	Positive
Informativeness	Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Hanaysha (2022), Zhang et al. (2019), Supotthamjaree & Srinaruewan (2021), Alalwan (2018)	Positive

Interaction	Kim & Ko (2010), Gautam & Sharma (2017), Moslehpour et al. (2020), Sharma et al. (2022), Imtiaz et al. (2019), Wagdi et al. (2022), Salhab et al. (2023), Alsoud et al. (2023), Ghafourzay & Parilti (2020), Bukhori et al. (2022), Ibrahim (2023), Sodom et al. (2023), Kumaradeepan et al. (2023), Onofrei et al. (2022), Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Hanaysha (2022), Alalwan (2018)	Positive
Interesting social media content	Sijabat et al. (2020)	Positive
Level of satisfaction with provided information	Sijabat et al. (2020)	Positive
Materialism beliefs	Chu et al. (2013), Chu et al. (2019)	Positive
Meaning Transfer	Hmoud et al. (2022)	Positive
Online advertisement	Balakrishnan et al. (2014)	Positive
Online communities	Balakrishnan et al. (2014), Wagdi et al. (2022), Salhab et al. (2023)	Positive
Peer communication	Pandey et al. (2018)	Positive
Perceived content quality	Onofrei et al. (2022)	Positive
Perceived financial value	Yu & Zheng (2021)	Positive
Perceived functional value	Yu & Zheng (2021)	Positive
Perceived green value	Sun & Xing (2022)	Positive
Perceived individual value	Yu & Zheng (2021)	Positive
Perceived relevance	Alalwan (2018), Hanaysha (2022)	Positive
Perceived risk	Wong (2018), AlAlawi et al. (2020)	Positive
Perceived social value	Yu & Zheng (2021)	Positive
Perceived source credibility	Onofrei et al. (2022)	Positive
<u>Perceived source homophily</u>	Onofrei et al. (2022)	Positive
Perceived usefulness	Sin et al. (2012), Kumar & Sharma (2020), Wong (2018)	Positive
Personalization	Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Zhang et al. (2019), Chuah et al. (2023)	Positive
Product information beliefs	Chu et al. (2013), Chu et al. (2019)	Positive
Product/services perception	Shrestha (2020)	Positive
Reputation	Sodom et al. (2023)	Positive
Sharing data	Manzoor et al. (2020)	Positive
Social commerce construct	Sin et al. (2012), Kumar & Sharma (2020)	Positive
Social influence	AlAlawi et al. (2020)	Positive
Social media	Bismo et al. (2019)	Positive
Social media advertisement	Noreen & Han (2015), Pütter (2017), Galdeano et al. (2019)	Positive
Social media Apps design and content quality	AlAlawi et al. (2020)	Positive
Social media based brand equity	Galdeano et al. (2019)	Positive
Social media based brand image	Galdeano et al. (2019)	Positive
Social media information sharing	Sun & Xing (2022)	Positive
Social media marketing	Savitri et al. (2022), Emini & Zeqiri (2021), Dewi et al. (2022), Putra & Aprilson (2022), Ellitan et al. (2022), Wagdi et al. (2022)	Positive
Social media marketing content type	Almohaimmeed (2019)	Positive
Social media motivation	Almohaimmeed (2019)	Positive
Social media usage	Khan et al. (2021)	Positive
Social media use for information	Hu & Zhu (2022)	Positive
Social media use for socializing	Hu & Zhu (2022)	Positive
Social network marketing	Prabowo et al. (2020)	Positive
Subjective norms	Pop et al. (2020)	Positive
Tailored advertising	Salhab et al. (2023)	Positive
Trendiness	Kim & Ko (2010), Gautam & Sharma (2017), Moslehpour et al. (2020), Sharma et al. (2022), Aggarwal & Mittal (2022), Alsoud et al. (2023), Ghafourzay & Parilti (2020), Bukhori et al. (2022), Ibrahim (2023), Chuah et al. (2023), Sodom et al. (2023), Kumaradeepan et al. (2023)	Positive
Trust	Sin et al. (2012), Manzoor et al. (2020), Shrestha (2020), Sodom et al. (2023), Kumaradeepan et al. (2023), Hmoud et al. (2022)	Positive
Trust	Wong (2018)	Negative
User generated content	Wagdi et al. (2022), Salhab et al. (2023), Morra et al. (2017)	Positive
Value corruption beliefs	Chu et al. (2013), Chu et al. (2019)	Positive
Viral marketing	Salhab et al. (2023)	Positive
Websites quality	Manzoor et al. (2020)	Positive

4.0 Implications, research gap and future research directions

What are the implications and research gaps identified in the existing literature on the impact of social media marketing on customer purchase intention?

Numerous studies (Shofiya & Fachira, 2021; Emini & Zeqiri, 2021; Ebrahimi et al., 2021; Ebrahimi et al., 2022; Bushara et al., 2023; Anas et al., 2023) have examined the relationship between social media marketing and customer purchase intention and have found that social media marketing significantly influences customer purchase intention. Companies can leverage this beneficial effect to continuously develop and enhance their product offering in order to better meet the needs and expectations of their clientele (Ebrahimi et al., 2021; Chrisniyanti & Fah, 2022; Nekomahmud et al., 2022).

In the current study, we found out that social media marketing is a multidimensional concept and most of the scholars have focused their attention on these seven dimensions that include: customization, entertainment, e-WOM, informativeness, interaction, trendiness, and trust. This review lays a firm foundation to assist researchers to better understand the concepts and dimensions of social media marketing for future investigations. Additionally, the review identifies multiple consequences or outcomes of customer purchase intention that include consumer buying intention, consumer purchase intention, customer purchase intention, green consumption intention, green purchase intention, online purchase intention, purchase decision, purchase intention, purchase intention of fast food products, purchase intention of luxury brands, tourists' purchase intention, and brand loyalty. However, the study reveals that the most used variable is purchase intention followed by customer purchase intention which variables ought to be upheld by future researchers.

Based on the review of the 50 research papers on the antecedents and consequences of social media marketing on customer purchase intention, we have identified several research gaps that need to be filled by conducting further research in this area. First, the findings show that the articles cover the major geographical regions in the world. However, more than half of these studies focus on Asia and Europe and only a few studies have paid attention to North and South America, Australia and Africa. As a result of this gap, there is need for future research to probe whether these Asian and European context findings can be applied to other geographical contexts. Secondly, it has been found that most research has been conducted in general industry sector, luxury brands sector, cosmetics sector, automobile sector, fast food sector and tourism sector. Limited research has been done in airlines industry, apparels industry, digital markets, telecoms industry and events sector. Hence, there is need for future research to focus in these industries as well. Thirdly, customization, entertainment, e-WOM, informativeness, interaction, trendiness, and trust are some of the widely used antecedents of social media marketing. Some variables like brand communication, brand consciousness, information sharing, online communities, perceived individual value and perceived relevance are used sparingly. Moreover the contemporary variables of social media marketing such as perceived value and social media influencers are totally ignored in this review. Marketers need to prioritise the perceived value dimension when measuring social media marketing since consumers are growing more and more value-conscious (El-Adly, 2019). Academics and business experts are also curious about social media influencers because of their potential as a tool for brand promotion. Social media influencers have caused a significant change in social media marketing (Cheung et al., 2023). It is unavoidable to include that dimension in the measurement of social media marketing because the popularity of social media influencers has prompted companies to partner with them. Fourthly, since social media marketing is a multi-dimensional construct, there has been inconsistency and confusion in its measurement. Consequently, this study provides a pool of nine contemporary antecedents of social media marketing that include: customization, entertainment, e-WOM, informativeness, interaction, trendiness, trust, perceived value and social media influencers that can be relied on by scholars investigating any aspect in social media marketing domain.

5.0 Conclusions

In Jai et al. (2021) opinion, a credible systematic literature review informs researchers of what is known, how it is known and where the academic direction of the research area lies. In this paper, an attempt has been made to review the existing literature of the impact of social media marketing on customer purchase intention from 2010 to 2024 by examining a total of 1,000 papers of which 50 papers were useful to this study. There are various contributions this study intends to make. First, we identified that most research in social media marketing has been carried out in Asia and Europe ignoring other parts of the world especially Africa. Hence, need for further research in Africa. Additionally, it was discovered that the most dominant sectors covered by social media scholars include luxury brands sector, cosmetics sector, automobile sector, fast food sector and tourism sector giving limited coverage in airlines industry, apparels industry, digital markets, and telecoms industry; giving research opportunities in the non-researched sectors. Thirdly, customization, entertainment, e-WOM, informativeness, interaction, trendiness, and trust are some of the widely used antecedents of social media marketing. However, this study identified two more antecedents: perceived value and social media influencers that are useful to the current business environment. Fourthly, since social media marketing is a multi-dimensional construct, there has been inconsistency and confusion in its measurement. This study provides a pool of nine contemporary antecedents of social media marketing that can be relied on by scholars investigating any aspect in social media marketing domain. After analyzing the existing empirical and conceptual research papers, it is concluded that social media marketing influences customer purchase intention. It may be the reason this concept is attracting a lot of attention from scholars and business practioners worldwide.

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